

Original Research Article

Antioxidant Potential of *Rhipsalis elliptica* Crude Extract and its Hypoglycemic Effect in Alloxan-Induced Diabetic Rats

*¹Isaac John Umaru, ²Kerenhappuch Isaac Umaru, ³Hauwa A. Umaru, ⁴Christopher Emeka Ahuchaogu and ⁵Maryam Ahmed Usman

Abstract

¹Department of Biochemistry, Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria

²Department of Biochemistry, University of Maiduguri Borno State Nigeria

³Department of Biochemistry, Modibbo Adama University of Technology Adamawa State Nigeria

⁴Department of Crop Production and Protection, Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria

⁵Department of Biochemistry, Adamawa State University Mubi (ADSU) Adamawa State Nigeria

*Corresponding Author's E-mail: umaruisaac@gmail.com

Traditional medicine has become a practice of global importance and has increasingly become an integral part of human society with regard to their therapeutic uses. Diabetes mellitus has been a menace to mankind from time immemorial. However, a natural product such as *Rhipsalis elliptica* crude extracts offers alternative treatment for diabetes mellitus. This research work was aimed at evaluating the antioxidant and antidiabetes activity of the methanol crude extract of *R. elliptica* in alloxan-induced diabetic rats. 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) was used to evaluate the antioxidant potential of the crude extract of *R. elliptica*, Alloxan (150mg/kg) was used intraperitoneally to induce diabetic in albino rats. Eight groups, normal control, diabetic control, treatment group including glibenclamide (71 µg/kg) and pioglitazone (429 µg/kg), were considered in the study. The effect of the crude extract on glucose, other biochemical, and the hematological parameters were evaluated. Diabetic control was on the days 7 of the study with 200, 300 and 400 mg/kg of the extract showing a glucose reduction of 77.32±34.11 µg/mL, 63.35±24.32 µg/mL, and 57.35±24.32 µg/mL. The antioxidant activity result indicated significant antioxidant potential in hexane, dichloromethane, ethyl acetate and methanol of 37.18, 24.12, 33.11 and 22.34 µg/mL respectively. This study showed that *R. elliptica* has an antidiabetic activity which may be through the antioxidant potential and can reduce the risk of eyes kidneys, peripheral nerves, heart, and blood vessels as a result of hyperglycemia. Antioxidant potential of *Rhipsalis elliptica* crude extract and its hypoglycemic effect in alloxan-induced diabetic rats is reported for the first.

Keywords: Alloxan, Antioxidant, Crude Extract, Hypoglycemic, Induced Diabetic, Rats, *Rhipsalis elliptica*

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus (DM) has been a threat to mankind from time immemorial and it is now creating more death rate wreaking great destruction worldwide (Tabish, 2007). It is a public health problems acknowledged as one of the most important killer diseases and a prominent cause of

death in low- and middle-income countries (WHO, 2014). The life the expectancy of diabetic patients is usually low compared to normal people (Andrade, 2010). Diabetes mellitus is a non-communicable disease in which there is a metabolic disorder of various etiologies described by

Figure 1. Showing the leaf-like part of *R. elliptica*

sustained hyperglycemia with disorders of carbohydrate, fat, and protein metabolism following defects in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both (Alberti et al., 2009). It is caused by the destruction of pancreatic β -cells or dysfunctional β -cell and insulin the resistance which results in hyperglycemia (ADA, 2014, Shrhata, 20016).

Over time, diabetic patients with poor glycemic control undergo microvascular and macrovascular complications including nephropathy, retinopathy, neuropathy, and cardiovascular diseases (Deshpande et al., 2008). These complications increase their suffering and are the major sources of expenses for patients with diabetes as well as increasing the financial burden of nations (Ray et al., 2005; Scully, 2012). Above and beyond insulin are other therapeutic options for the treatment of type 1 diabetes which include transplantation of whole organ pancreas and isolated islets, marred by both lack and quality of the donor's pancreas (Mtsumoto et al., 2009; Aziz et al., 2013).

Diabetes, caused by inherited and/or acquired deficiency in production of insulin by the pancreas (type 1) or by ineffectiveness of insulin (type 2), can as well be caused by a number of biological factors which are related to hyperglycaemia and hyperlipidaemia which may lead to death (Tahmouzi et al., 2014)

However, numerous agents that are currently used for the treatment of type 2 diabetes are facing limited efficacy and tolerability (Xu et al., 2014). Although insulin and other artificially synthesized anti-diabetes drugs like acarbose and voglibose are effective for the management of diabetes, they are far from satisfying the urgency for their enormous costs or undesirable side effects. Thus, searching for alternative anti-diabetic natural products from plants has received great attention.

Rhipsalis elliptica is a species of the plant in the family Cactaceae, it is endemic to Brazil. Its natural habitat is

subtropical and tropical moist low land forest. It is threatened by habitat loss. It belongs to the kingdom Plantae, class of Magnoliopsida, an order Caryophyllales, a family of Cactaceae.

The plant is used as ornamental among the Sarawakians. It is at its best in a light to partially shaded location without too strong sunshine. Ideal locations are east or west-facing windows. South windows are also suitable, but the strong sun must be significantly weakened by curtains or shade of others plants (Hunt et al., 2006)

The ideal temperature for the plant range between 18 and 24 °C throughout the year. The night-time temperatures can drop quite a few degrees, but fluctuations of more than 10 to 12 ° C within one day should be avoided not to destroy the beauty of the plant and because of its sensitivity to lime environment the epiphytic cacti prefer clean water and humus loose soil for the cultivation. The first voucher *R. elliptica* was reported as *R. elliptica* G.A. Lindberg, A. Calvente 214 (Calvente, et al., 2011).

The objective of this study was to evaluate hypoglycaemic effects of the *R. elliptica* methanol leaves crude extracts with normal and alloxan-induced diabetic rats, evaluate the cytotoxicity from the plant leaves crude extract. This was the first time this study was carried out in this plant *R. elliptica*. **Figure 1**

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The leaf-like part of the selected plant *R. elliptica* as shown in Figure 1 were collected in Kota-Samarahan in January and was identified as *R. elliptica* by Prof Hauwa A. Umaru School of pure and applied science Moddibo Adama University of Technology Yola.

Chemical and reference drug

All chemicals and Drugs (Alloxan Monohydrate) used in this investigation were of analytical grade and were obtained from Sigma Chemical Co., St Louis, USA. Insulin (reference drug) was obtained from Medical Resource SDN BHD Kuching, Sarawak. DPPH, Brine shrimps

Preparation of the extract

The plant part (leaves) were dried in a laboratory drying site, the dried leaves was made into powder using electric grinder. The extraction was carried out by conventional extraction by soaking the powdered sample (1000g) in ethanol 1:3 (sample: solvent) in a 5-liter flask at room temperature for 7 days. The resulting the methanol solution was filtered and residue was again re-extracted with fresh methanol for 72 hrs and filtered. Both the filtrates were combined and evaporated to dryness with a rotary evaporator under reduced pressure 50 °C

Antioxidant test

The antioxidant test based on the free radical scavenging assay of compound 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picryl-hydrazyl (DPPH) was used to evaluate the antioxidant properties of the crude extract from hexane, dichloromethane, ethyl acetate, and methanol. The measurement was based on the method described by Umaru et al., (2019). 5 mg of the crude extract was introduced and mixed in 5 mL methanol to produce 1000 µg/mL. Four other concentration were prepared at 50, 100, 250 and 500 µg/mL for each crude extract. 3 mL of 0.1 mM solution of DPPH in methanol was each added into the five series of prepared concentrations of sample solution of 1 mL. The solution was mixed vigorously and left to stand at room temperature for 30 minutes in the dark after which its absorbance was measured at 517 nm. The value in triplicate was determined using Log dose inhibition curve which was performed by using PRISM version 3.02 software.

Diabetic test

Experimental Animals

Adult albino rats (Wister strains 48 in numbers) weighing about 150-200 g body weight were used for this study. They were put in cages at room temperature (20-27°C) under 12/12 night/dark. They were maintained on standard animal pellets (vital feeds, Grand's cereals and

oil meal) and water ad libitum for a period of one week before the commencement of the work. The standard procedures and protocol for the animal experimental study were observed for the study. They were randomly divided into eight groups of six rats each and treated as shown in Table 1. The experiment was conducted based on the adherence ethical protocol.

Ethical Consideration

The experimental protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee on animal use of Federal University Wukari (with a protocol ID: RA/22/2019), and was carried out in strict compliance with the National Research Council guidelines on the care and use of laboratory animals.

Experimental Procedure

Induction of Diabetes

Except for the rats in group 1 (control), DM was experimentally induced in the animals in groups 2–7, after fasting them overnight by intraperitoneal administration of alloxan monohydrate dissolved in normal saline (150 mg/kg) (Akhtar et al., 2002). Three days of alloxan administration by determination of the tail vein blood glucose level. The tips of the tail (approximately 2 mm) were clipped off using a sterile blade and 1-2 drops of the blood from the cut surface was used for the measurement of blood glucose concentration using strip (one-touch test strip). The rats with blood glucose level above 11 mmol/L (250 to 300 mg/dL) were considered diabetic and was used as diabetic rats in the study (Emordi et al., 2018)

Animal treatment

The treatment of the animals via oral route lasted for 14 days. Group 1 (normal control), Group 2 (Diabetic control), Groups 3 and 4 received 71 µg/kg of glibenclamide, and 429 µg/kg of pioglitazone, respectively. Groups 5, 6, 7 and 8, received 100, 200, 300 and 400 mg/kg of the leaves extract of *R. elliptica*, respectively, as reported by Emordi et al. (2018) with little modification where the extract was administered to the normal control. However, group 2 was not treated with the extract as it represented the diabetic control. During the treatment period, the weight of the animals and the fasting blood glucose (FBG) measurements were determined with a weighing scale and a glucometer (using the tail vein), respectively, every 2 days from the beginning of the treatment (day 1) to the last day of the experiment (15th day).

Table 1. Free radical scavenging activity against DPPH radical of *R. elliptica* extract

Plant	Crude Extract	R ²	IC ₅₀ (µg/mL)
Leaves	Hexane	0.9847	37.18
	Dichloromethane	0.9998	24.12
	Ethyl acetate	0.9897	33.11
	Methanol	0.9658	22.34
	Ascorbic acid	0.9999	2.73

Figure 2. Radical scavenging activity of various crude extracts of *R. elliptica*

Sample Analysis

The blood was collected on the 15th day through the ocular puncture into heparinized bottles for biochemical assays, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) bottles for hematological assays, and plain bottles for insulin assay and the rats sacrificed. The blood samples with anticoagulants were centrifuged within five minutes of collection for 10 min at 4,000 g. By precipitation and modified enzymatic procedures from Sigma Diagnostics. (Migliori et al., 2017; Crook, 2006). Also, creatinine and the enzymes (aspartate aminotransferase (Bagberi et al 2000), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), and alkaline phosphatase (ALP). obtained from the plasma were evaluated using standard enzymatic assay methods (Horder et al., 1991). The Hematological parameters assay includes: RBC (Red blood cells), WBC (white blood count), Hb (hemoglobin), PCV/HCT (packed cell volume), MCV (mean corpuscular volume), MCHC (mean corpuscular hemoglobin volume) and Platelets

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Free radical scavenging activities of the leaf-like part of *R. elliptica* from different solvent system was evaluated using DPPH a stable free radical method that is sensitive in determining the antioxidant activity of plant extracts. Natural antioxidant presents in plants scavenge harmful free radicals from the human body. These antioxidants exert their mode of action by suppressing the formation of reactive oxygen species either by inhibition of enzyme or

by chelating trace elements (Asok Kumar *et al.*, 2009). The antioxidant effect of the leaves extract of *R. elliptica* is shown in [Table 1](#) and [Figure 2](#). The result showed that methanol extract exhibited strong antioxidant potential with IC₅₀ values of 22.34 µg/mL and is in agreement with the work of Mariya and Reena (2007) in which they reported that methanol extract was found to be the most effective antioxidant.

Diabetes mellitus have received great care both in a modern and traditional medical specialty. Diabetes is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by abnormally high blood glucose level and the evacuation of excess glucose in urine (Shourie and Kalra, 2013). It is the most common endocrine disorder currently affecting a large ratio of the population worldwide. The number of people with diabetes is on the increase due to population growth, aging, and increasing prevalence of obesity and physical inactivity (Gosh *et al.*, 2004). With the increasing risk of developing complications of the eyes kidneys, peripheral nerves, heart and blood vessels (Athanasakis *et al.*, 2010; Olaokun *et al.*, 2016)

These complications can be prevented by ensuring that the blood glucose measurement are within satisfactory limits (42). Therefore, an important way of controlling diabetes mellitus is by the use of agents that reduce postprandial hyperglycemia by suppressing the Hydrolysis of carbohydrates.

Findings of this study revealed that the blood glucose levels of the diabetic induced rats treated with *R. elliptica* were comparable to the normal control. Nevertheless, diabetic control was achieved on the 7th day with a marked glucose reduction of 123.12±34.11 µg/mL,

Tables 2. Induction of diabetics, standards and the treatment of experimental rats plant extracts

Groups	Induced Diabetics with 150mg/kg/bwt alloxan							
	Normal Control	Diabetic control	Glibenclamide 429 µg/kg	Pioglitazone 76 µg/kg	Treatment Groups with <i>Rhipsalis elliptica crude</i>			
					100	200	300	400
	Distilled water/food	Distilled water/food	Distilled water/food	Distilled water/food	Distilled water/food	Distilled water/food	Distilled water/food	Distilled water/food

Table 3. Effects of the leaves crude extract of *R. elliptica* on blood glucose (mg/dL) in alloxan-induced rats.

Parameters	Induced Diabetics							
	Control	Diabetic control	glibenclamide	pioglitazone	Treatment Groups with <i>R. elliptica crude</i> (mg/kg)			
					100	200	300	400
0	85.55±0.67	77.44±2.33	77.11±20.12	79.77±7.76	66.24±4.33	60.33±4.33	63.33±4.33	60.25±4.33
1	95.44±1.45	255.21±1.16	333.6±13.24	366.11±8.55	363.12±12.00	344.22±12.00	387.33±12.00	387.22±12.00*
3	84.33±0.12	264.22±0.77	232.0±16.22	210.17±24.12	215.16±18.23	206.12±18.23	210.11±18.23	209.23±23.11*
5	82.12±1.23	266.13±1.11	219.43±0.98*	150.57±22.0	188.23±12.9	78.18±14.0	121.13±23.0	113.13±11.12*
7	76.22±0.26	277.41±1.24	199.11±10.00*	177.4±33.23	123.12±34.11	77.32±34.11	63.35±24.32	57.35±24.32*
9	88.11±1.33	289.33±2.00	133.23±11.00*	222.31±45.00	88.34±25.33	82.12±22.16	79.14±18.67	59.33±17.14*
11	82.25±0.78	298.56±1.21	110.0±23.15	199.33±21.23	76.29±18.00	65.18±18.00	54.15±16.12	50.71±22.10*
13	80.66±0.88	311.22±2.11	98.25±6.34	150.0±2.35	68.27±3.00	67.27±3.00	51.27±3.00	46.45±1.220
15	76.11±1.22	320.51±2.19	92.12±44.11	155.56±44.32	59.15±33.14	53.15±33.14	48.17±4.174	42.18±4.14*

Significant difference ($p < 0.05$; $n = 7$) between the mean \pm SD

77.32±34.11 µg/mL, 63.35±24.32 µg/mL, and 57.35±24.32 µg/mL, respectively as shown in Table 3 following the administration of 100, 200, 300, and 400 mg/kg of the *R. elliptica cruda* extract. This glucose control was sustained until the end of the study.

The reference drugs glibenclamide and pioglitazone had a plasma glucose reduction of 199.11±10.00 and 177.4±33.23, respectively on the 7th day. The antidiabetic activity of *R. elliptica* maybe from the potential of the crude extract of, Hexane, Dichloromethane, Ethyl acetate, and Methanol of 37.18, 24.12, 33.11, and 22.34 µg/mL, respectively when compared to the ascorbic of 2.73 µg/mL

The effect of the crude extract of *R. elliptica* on the bodyweight of the rats is observed in Table 4. The doses rate of the crude extract at 200, 300, and 400 mg/kg caused a significant reduction in the weight of the rats from day 7 through to days 15. While 100 mg/kg causes little reduction from days 9 through to days 15. The weights of the diabetic rats that were not treated reduced significantly from the 7th to the 15th day of the study.

The effect of *R. elliptica* crude extract on the blood components is reported in Table 4. The crude extract caused no significant alteration in the white blood cell (WBC), red blood cell (RBC) hemoglobin concentration (HGb), packed cell

volume (PVC), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH), mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC), and the platelets (PLT) results when compared to the control as shown in Table 4. However, the drugs used for the control of diabetic glibenclamide and pioglitazone caused a significant ($p < 0.05$) elevation in the WBC counts of the group of diabetic rats compared to the control.

The effect of *R. elliptica* crude extract on plasma biochemical parameters as shown in Table 5 caused no significant alteration in the plasma creatinine urea, protein, and albumin, ALT, AST and ALP measurements of the diabetic rats compared to the control. However, the

Table 4. Effect of the crude extract of *R. elliptica* on body weight (g)

Parameters	Control	Diabetic control	Induced Diabetics					
			glibenclamide	pioglitazone	Treatment Groups with <i>Rhipsalis elliptica</i> crude (mg/kg)			
					100	200	300	400
1	144±0.44	122.8±2.11	132.56±4.12	144.12±0.18	134.39±3.22	138.56±3.56	122.88±1.33	121.21±3.12
3	142±1.26	127.6±1.37	133.63±3.22	139.11±2.56	129.28±2.45	140.21±4.11	135.49±2.34	122.33±2.27
5	143±1.33	121.4±1.67	138.57±2.67	122.20±2.23	129.19±1.96	131.11±2.78	126.58±2.67	124.44±1.89
7	140±0.45	127.9±2.56	129.31±3.44	120.45±3.12	123.55±2.56	126.56±3.33	134.67±1.77	128.38±2.34
9	150±1.37	130.6±2.78	137.43±2.22	131.67±1.19	129.47±3.46	117.42±1.87	109.29±1.89	102.74±2.56
11	149±0.67	129.2±1.93	133.23±2.78	129.47±1.14	122.54±2.44	123.37±2.46	118.38±2.38	115.57±1.88
13	148±1.22	128.7±1.77	129.09±1.86	119.23±2.00	120.24±1.89	128.56±2.79	122.45±1.66	118.43±2.17
15	147±1.57	126.5±2.11	130.11±2.49	126.18±1.99	120.33±1.79	118.21±1.88	114.11±1.89	111.25±2.48

Table 5. Effects of the crude extract of *R. elliptica* on the blood components

Parameters	Control	Diabetic control	Induced Diabetics					
			glibenclamide	pioglitazone	Treatment Groups with <i>Rhipsalis elliptica</i> crude			
					100	200	300	400
WBC ($\times 10^9/L$)	7.7±0.33	9.34±0.56	12.00±0.79	11.02±1.00	6.30±0.77	6.42±0.66	6.11±0.69	5.9±0.77
RBC ($\times 10^{12}/L$)	6.3±0.43	7.01±0.66	4.96±0.66	5.11±0.28	6.00±0.59	6.20±0.37	6.22±0.74	6.00±0.47
Hgb (g/dl)	13.0±0.45	13.33±1.23	11.0±0.57	11.33±0.17	10.33±1.33	10.40±0.77	10.42±0.67	10.12±0.56
PCV (%)	39.67±2.78	39.45±3.56	30.03±0.85	30.02±1.33	31.23±4.66	32.00±1.86	32.89±0.55	32.14±1.23
MCV (fL)	69.77±8.22	59.76±2.44	54.50±0.93	55.05±1.65	57.56±19.23	56.17±1.99	57.87±3.39	58.89±3.88
MCH (pg)	20.8±1.55	18.66±1.00	18.89±0.71	15.57±1.98	16.46±0.65	16.32±0.67	16.44±0.82	16.78±1.00
MCHC (g/dl)	30.03±0.98	33.00±0.45	32.79±0.28	30.49±0.17	29.66±0.45	29.13±0.73	30.08±0.11	29.45±0.99
PLT ($\times 10^9/L$)	917.88±5.67	963.0±18.11	943.88±0.64	959.06±18.23	966.11±7.76	959.20±12.27	948.11±18.12	911.08±15.67

Table 6. Effects of the crude extract of *R. elliptica* on plasma biochemical parameters

Parameters	Control	Diabetic control	Induced Diabetics					
			glibenclamide	pioglitazone	Treatment Groups with <i>R. elliptica</i> crude			
					100	200	300	400
AST(U/L)	20.55±3.87	30.4±1.45	29.34±0.23	28.11±2.89	22.11±1.22	24.33±1.98	26.77±2.00	25.98±1.00
ALT(U/L)	14.89±0.98	18.23±1.76	25.39±0.42	19.56±3.46	17.21±4.01	19.18±2.12	23.14±1.88	24.66±2.11
ALP (U/L)	29.67±1.29	35.11±1.45	29.56±1.27	22.75±2.99	20.33±3.41	22.15±4.56	23.78±5.23	26.00±5.66
Creatinine	1.00±0.22	1.23±1.44*	0.98±2.00	0.78±1.67	1.11±0.03	1.08±0.04	0.96±0.02	0.87±0.05*
Urea	36.88±6.78	45.77±2.34	38.55±1.67	35.16±3.00	33.22±0.98	31.11±2.88	29.58±1.99	35.21±2.88
Protein	5.98±7.66	7.34±0.45	6.00±0.78	5.87±0.45	5.67±0.78	5.89±0.77	6.00±0.59	6.88±0.46
Albumin	3.38±0.78	4.36±0.56	4.12±0.35	3.77±0.32	3.58±0.44	3.46±0.32	3.12±0.44	3.07±0.34

plasma creatinine measurements were significantly ($p < 0.05$) elevated in diabetic rats not treated.

CONCLUSION

The antidiabetic activity was performed with the aqueous crude extract of *R. elliptica*. The result of the study showed an observed concentration-dependent decrease in glucose levels in the treated groups with the most significant value was able to increase insulin secretion from the regenerated pancreatic beta cells. This will contribute to the discovery of novel phytochemicals that could aide in combating especially diabetics that is engulfing the health sector worldwide. Such discovery will help especially in the underdeveloped and tropical countries that have been ravaged by war, insurgencies and natural disasters.

RECOMMENDATION

More studies on the plant *R. elliptica* for its possible usage as an agent to control Hyperglycemia should be considered.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author thanks Mr. Benedict Sambling for the plant's information and technical assistance and Federal University Wukari for the study leave.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- Alberti K. G. M. M, Eckel RH, Grundy SM, Zimmet PZ, Cleeman JI, Donato KA, Smith Jr, S. C. (2009). Harmonizing the metabolic syndrome: a joint interim statement of the international diabetes federation task force on epidemiology and prevention; national heart, lung, and blood institute; American heart association; world heart federation; international atherosclerosis society; and international association for the study of obesity. *Circulation*, 120(16), 1640-1645.
- American Diabetes Association. (2014). Diagnosis and classification of diabetes mellitus. *Diabetes care*, 37(Supplement 1), S81-S90.
- Andrade FC (2010). Measuring the impact of diabetes on life expectancy and disability-free life expectancy among older adults in Mexico. *J. Gerontol. Series B: Psychological Sciences and Social Sciences*, 65(3), 381-389.
- Asok Kumar K, Uma Maheswari M, Sivashanmugam AT, Subhadra Devi V, Subhashini N, Ravi TK (2009). Free radical scavenging and antioxidant activities of *Glinus oppositifolius* (carpet weed) using different *in-vitro* assay systems. *Pharmaceutical Biology*, 47(6), 474-482.
- Athanasakis, K., Ollandezos, M., Angeli, A., Gregoriou, A., Geitona, M., & Kyriopoulos, J. (2010). Estimating the direct cost of Type 2 diabetes in Greece: the effects of blood glucose regulation on patient cost. *Diabetic Medicine*, 27(6), 679-684.
- Aziz MTA, El-Asmar MF, Rezaq AM Mahfouz, S. M., Wassef, M. A., Fouad, H. H., & Taha, F. M. (2013). The effect of a novel curcumin derivative on pancreatic islet regeneration in experimental type-1 diabetes in rats (long term study). *Diabetology & metabolic syndrome*, 5(1), 75.
- Bagheri H, Michel F, Lapeyre-Mestre M, Lagier E, Cambus JP, Valdiguie P, Montastruc JL (2000). Detection and incidence of drug-induced liver injuries in hospital: a prospective analysis from laboratory signals. *Brit. J. Clin. Pharmacol.* 50(5), 479-484.
- Calvente A, Zappi DC, Forest F, Lohmann LG (2011). Molecular phylogeny of tribe Rhipsalideae (Cactaceae) and taxonomic implications for Schlumbergera and Hatiora. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, 58(3), 456-468.
- Crook M (2006). *Clinical chemistry & metabolic medicine* (Vol. 426). London: Hodder Arnold.32
- Deshpande AD, Harris-Hayes M, Schootman M (2008). Epidemiology of diabetes and diabetes-related complications. *Physical therapy*, 88(11), 1254-1264.
- Ghosh T, Mitra P, Jha DK, Mitra PK (2004). *Abrus precatorius* Linnaeus and its biological activities- A Review. *World J. Pharm. Pharm. Sci.*, 6(8), 352-368
- Hörder M, Elser RC, Gerhardt W, Mathieu M, Sampson EJ (1991). Approved recommendation of IFCC methods for the measurement of catalytic concentration of enzymes. VII: IFCC method for creatine kinase (ATP: creatine N-phosphotransferase EC 2.7. 3.2). *Eur. J. Clin. Chem. Clin. Biochem.* 29(7), 435-456.
- Hunt DR, Taylor NP, Charles G (2006). *New cactus lexicon*. dh books.
- Mariya S, Reena L (2017). Evaluation of pigments as antioxidant and antibacterial agents from *Beta vulgaris* Linn. *Int. J. Cur. Pharm. Res.* 9, 33-37.
- Matsumoto S, Noguchi H, Hatanaka N, Shimoda M, Kobayashi N, Jackson A, Levy MF (2009). Estimation of donor usability for islet transplantation in the United States with the Kyoto islet isolation method. *Cell transplantation*, 18(5-6), 549-556.
- Migliori GB, Pontali E, Sotgiu G, Centis R, D'Ambrosio L, Tiberi S, Esposito S (2017). Combined use of delamanid and bedaquiline to treat multidrug-resistant and extensively drug-resistant tuberculosis: a systematic review. *Int. J. Molecular Sci.* 18(2), 341.
- Olaokun OO, McGaw LJ, van Rensburg IJ, Eloff JN, Naidoo V (2016). Antidiabetic activity of the ethyl acetate fraction of *Ficus lutea* (Moraceae) leaf extract: comparison of an *in vitro* assay with an *in vivo* obese mouse model. *BMC complementary and alternative medicine*, 16(1), 110.
- Ray JA, Valentine WJ, Secnik K., Oglesby AK, Cordony A, Gordoia A, Palmer AJ (2005). Review of the cost of diabetes complications in Australia, Canada, France, Germany, Italy and Spain. *Current medical research and opinion*, 21(10), 1617-1629.
- Scully T (2012). Diabetes in Numbers. *Nature*, 485, S2-S3.
- Shehata M (2016). Monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 (MCP-1) is associated with pancreatic beta-cell dysfunction in type 2 Diabetes mellitus. *Al-Azhar J. Pharm. Sci.* 53(1), 29-38.
- Shourie A, Kalra K (2013). Analysis of phytochemical constituents and Pharmacological properties of *Abrus precatorius* L. *Int. J. Pharm. Biol. Sci.* 4(1), 91-101.
- Tabish SA (2007). Is diabetes becoming the biggest epidemic of the twenty-first century? *Int. J. Health Sci.* 1(2), 5-8.
- Tahmouzi S (2014). Optimization of polysaccharides from Zagros oak leaf using RSM: antioxidant and antimicrobial activities. *Carbohydrate polymers*, 106, 238-246.
- World Health Organization. (2014). Global health estimates: deaths by cause, age, sex and country, 2000-2012. *Geneva*, WHO, 9.
- Xu X, Wang G, Zhou T, Chen L, Chen J, Shen X (2014). Novel approaches to drug discovery for the treatment of type 2 diabetes. *Expert opinion on drug discovery*, 9(9), 1047-1058.